

**Supplementary Materials of “Function Decomposition Tree with
Causality-First Perspective and Systematic Description of Problems in
Materials Informatics”**

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1 Example of automatic generation of function decomposition network

In sample/descriptorTarget in the repository [1], the results of

```
$ python cx_network_main.py --graphviz_FDN *.cx
```

are shown in SM Figure 1, and separately placed, too. The functional decomposition network corresponding to Figure 8 in the main text is shown in SM Figure 2.

SM Figure 1. Automatically generated function decomposition network from workflow.

SM Figure 2. Function decomposition network the large goal of which is “Obtain function decomposition network”.

2 Applications 1: Description of Materials Informatics by Conventional Text

In this study, I, J, K are the indices of the atoms and p, r, q are the indices of the crystal translation operation. The crystals are defined in three-dimensional space and are equivalent (invariant) to translational motion T_p , rotation, and atomic reordering to I or I_p .

1.1 Association with descriptor with target variable for the prediction model

Let us consider an example of regression prediction models to search for useful materials from the atomic coordinates of a material. The relationship among atomic coordinates, the descriptor, and the crystal target variable have been described in three main ways.

Let y be the target variable, P be the size of the feature vector, $\vec{x}_I \in R^P$ be the atomic feature vector at the I -th site, and $\vec{X} \in R^P$ be the crystal feature vector. The regression of the target variable using this \vec{X} was considered. There is an example of Gaussian process regression using the SOAP descriptor (GAP) as \vec{X} [2], which is herein referred as the direct crystal descriptor generation way.

As an alternative approach, let y_I be a hypothetical target variable for site I , assuming the following relationship,

$$y = \sum_I y_I(\vec{x}_I)$$

$$y_I(\vec{x}_I) = f_{\text{atom}}(\vec{x}_I), \quad (2)$$

where $f_{\text{atom}}(\vec{x}_I)$ is a regression function for an atomic target variable. The validity of the assumption was tested by the regression performance. This form was utilized by a neural network regression using Behler's symmetry function as a descriptor [3] that is termed as the atomic target variable way.

The way was separately defined to generate \vec{X} with a function g via \vec{x}_n as

$$\vec{X} = g(\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_1, \dots, \vec{x}_N)$$

This was termed as the atomic descriptor-derived crystal descriptor way, where g can be the summation, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum. In practice, this way is widely used in generation of atomic reordering invariant descriptors from chemical formulae. [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9]

If a linear function is used for g , let x_{ip} be the p component of \vec{x}_i ,

$$y = \sum_I y_I(\vec{x}_I) = \sum_I \sum_p c_p x_{Ip} = \sum_p c_p X_p, \quad (3)$$

then the atomic descriptor-derived crystal descriptor way is equivalent to the atomic target variable way. Herein, c_p is the regression coefficient of X_p , where $X_p = \sum_i x_{ip}$, i.e., function g is the sum of all components. Thus, the function g in linearity is classified as the atomic descriptor-derived crystal descriptor way. The linear regression is advantageous in obtaining the regression faster and can avoid overfitting with penalty

terms in Lasso and Ridge regressions. This form was utilized to obtain a sparse representation of the descriptor with linear regression using Behler's symmetry function as the descriptor [10]. The SNAP descriptor was also used by the linear regression [11]. SM Table 1 summarizes the relationships between the descriptors explained above and the target variables.

SM Table 1: The procedure for obtaining the target variable from the atomic coordinates is shown.

	step 1	step 2	step 3
Atomic target variables way	Obtain atomic descriptors from atomic coordinates	Associate atomic descriptors with atomic target variables	Transform atomic target variables into crystal target variables
Atomic descriptor-derived crystal descriptor way	Obtain atomic descriptors from atomic coordinates	Transform atomic descriptors to crystal descriptor	Associate crystal descriptors with crystal target variables
Direct crystal descriptor generation way		Obtain crystal descriptor directly from atomic coordinates	Associate crystal descriptors with crystal target variables

1.2 Atomic Positions in Crystals

Herein, we defined a material as with a crystal and its physical properties as attributes. Crystals are defined by the elemental name 'elm' (and possibly its isotopes) attribute and a list vector associated with the atomic position \mathbf{S} attribute as $((elm_1, S_1), (elm_2, S_2), \dots, (elm_N, S_N))$, which was written as $\{(I; 'element': elm_I, 'postion': \mathbf{S}_I)\}_{I=1}^N$. Therefore, extracting the elemental name attribute provides us with $\{(I; 'element':$

$elm_I\}_{I=1}^N$ and the atomic position attribute is $\{(I; \text{'position': } \mathbf{S}_I)\}_{I=1}^N$. The indices after '}' are omitted hereafter.

For a crystal, the atoms exist at the position $\mathbf{R}_{Ip} = \mathbf{S}_I + \mathbf{T}_p$ (atomic position in the extended cells, abbreviated as **extended position**), where the periodic atomic positions are generated from translating \mathbf{S}_I using the translation vector \mathbf{T}_p . Moreover, the atomic positions (atomic distribution) of a crystal can be defined as $\{(Ip: R_{Ip})\}_{Ip}$, and the relative position list of a crystal can be defined as $\{(I; \text{'relative position': } \{\mathbf{R}_{Jq} - \mathbf{R}_I\}_{Jq})\}$.

1.3 Atomic-element-derived Features

Features derived from atomic element are generated from each element name, including continuous, discrete, and categorical quantities. The feature of categorical quantities is a list (vector quantities).

1.4 Features of Categorical Quantities

The representatives of the categorical quantities are atomic number, Mendeleev number, row and column number on the periodic table, and the electron configuration for each valence orbital of an atom. For instance, given an elm , an entire vector (hydrogen or not, He or not, Li or not, ...) is generated.

A categorical quantity containing a number in the name is usually a discrete quantity within a homogeneous name range. For instance, the d-electron valence electron configuration of an isolated atom (d^1, d^2, \dots, d^{10}) can be treated as a discrete quantity from 0 to 10. Although it is a discrete value, the generated value can be algebraically calculated as a continuous quantity.

Random alloy is a form of material in which more than one element is randomly mixed at the location of the atoms present. The Bethe-Slater curve of theoretical

parameters [12] and the Slater-Pauling curve of physical properties [13], [14] for random alloys are known to be based on the atomic number as a continuous quantity of the transition metals. The first-principles calculations provide the virtual crystal approximation [15], where the atomic number is a continuous quantity. In addition, the more advanced coherent potential approximation is used in the KKR method [16]. Thus, atomic numbers are treated as discrete values, and furthermore as continuous quantities by performing algebraic calculations for practical materials science applications.

1.5 Features of Continuous Quantities

Atoms are composed of protons and neutrons, and isotopes with the same number of protons (atomic number) but different numbers of neutrons also exist. In addition, the number of neutrons needs to be specified as an attribute of the element. The use of isotope is explicitly documented by experiment and theory. As the atomic mass affects the phonon frequency in superconductors, the isotope mass is an important feature determining whether the superconducting mechanism occurs due to the BCS mechanism [17].

In context, electrical affinity and ionization energy are defined as the energies required to obtain or release an electron from an isolated atom. Usually, their values are evaluated from experimental values.

The spin Hamiltonian features used in theory can be descriptor features for magnetization and magnetic transition temperatures [18]. The spin momentum features of 3d systems such as that in transition metals can be S, whereas, in rare-earth elements (f-electrons), the coefficient of the effective spin-spin interaction is $(g_J - 1)J_{4f}$, which is the spin directional projection of J_{4f} , where g_J is Landé's g-factor. The valence number

(charged state) of rare earth elements often acquires the value in the crystal. Therefore, it is also important to know that certain elements, Ce, Yb, Eu and Sm, can acquire more than one valence number in crystals [19].

1.6 Isolated Atom Features from First-Principles Calculations

The first-principles calculation of isolated atoms can be easily executed for a given element name in various software packages. A theoretical description of the first-principles calculation for electronic structure is presented herein. The operator for obtaining the total energy of the system in which the electrons and atoms are interacting is defined as

$$\hat{H} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_i \nabla_i^2 - \sum_i \sum_I \frac{Z_I}{|r_i - R_I|} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \neq j} \frac{1}{|r_i - r_j|} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_I \nabla_I^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_I \sum_J \frac{Z_I Z_J}{|R_I - R_J|},$$

where i, j are the indices of electrons and I, J are the indices of atoms. The total energy can be evaluated considering the expected value of the total wave function. In practice, performing the calculation in a short period of time is challenging owing to the interaction among electrons, thus requiring approximations.

The density functional theory is an approximation method that significantly accelerates this calculation. The density functional calculations for isolated atoms are briefly described based on Martin's book [20]. In density functional theory, the total energy is a function of the electron density $n(r)$. In addition, electrons have spin degrees of freedom, the total number of electrons is the sum of the number of electrons in up and down spins ($N = N^\uparrow + N^\downarrow$), and $n(r)$ is obtained from the wave function $\psi_a^\sigma(r)$. Let $\psi_a^\sigma(r)$ satisfy the orthonormal condition with respect to a and σ , where a is the index representing the eigenstate of the wave function. Therefore, $n(r)$ can be defined as

$$n(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\sigma} n^{\sigma}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{\sigma} \sum_a^{N^{\sigma}} |\psi_a^{\sigma}(\mathbf{r})|^2$$

The total energy E_{KS} in the density functional theory can be defined as

$$E_{KS} = T_S + E_{ext}[n] + H_{hartree}[n] + E_{XC}[n] + E_{II},$$

T_S is the kinetic energy of electrons in a non-interacting system obtained from the wave function,

$$T_S = \sum_s \sum_i^{N^s} \langle \psi_i^s | -\frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 | \psi_i^s \rangle.$$

Subsequently, the other terms were derived from the electron density. The second term in \hat{H} is

$$E_{ext}[n] = \int d\mathbf{r} V_{ext}(\mathbf{r}) n(\mathbf{r}).$$

The third item in \hat{H} is the electron–electron interaction term, which consists of the Hartree term $H_{hartree}[n]$ of E_{KS} ,

$$H_{hartree}[n] = \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{r} \int d\mathbf{r}' \frac{n(\mathbf{r})n(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|},$$

and contributions from exchange–correlation interaction $E_{XC}[n]$ of E_{KS} , which was initially obtained by separately evaluating the total energy of the uniform electron gas using the first-principles Monte Carlo and many-body perturbation expansion methods, and thereafter regressed on a simple function.

The E_{KS} is a function of $\psi_a^\sigma(\mathbf{r})$ via $n^\sigma(\mathbf{r})$, and the most stable electronic state (ground state) satisfies the following variational conditions for fixed atomic positions,

$$\frac{\delta E_{KS}}{\delta \psi_a^\sigma} = \frac{\delta T_S}{\delta \psi_a^\sigma(\mathbf{r})} + \left[\frac{\delta E_{ext}}{\delta n^\sigma(\mathbf{r})} + \frac{\delta E_{hartree}}{\delta n^\sigma(\mathbf{r})} + \frac{\delta E_{XC}}{\delta n^\sigma(\mathbf{r})} \right] \frac{\delta n^\sigma(\mathbf{r})}{\delta \psi_a^\sigma(\mathbf{r})} = 0.$$

The introduction of the orthonormalization condition $\langle \psi_a^\sigma | \psi_a^{\sigma'} \rangle = \delta_{aa'} \delta_{\sigma\sigma'}$ and the Lagrange multipliers of the coefficient ϵ_a^σ with the constraint results in

$$\left[-\frac{1}{2} \nabla^2 + V_{KS}(r) \right] \psi_a^\sigma(r) = \epsilon_a^\sigma \psi_a^\sigma(r)$$

$$V_{KS}(r) = V_{ext}(r) + \frac{\delta E_{hartree}}{\delta n^\sigma(r)} + \frac{\delta E_{XC}}{\delta n^\sigma(r)} = V_{ext}(r) + V_{hartree}(r) + V_{XC}^\sigma(r).$$

ϵ_a^σ is a Lagrange coefficient that satisfies the relationship

$$\epsilon_a^\sigma = \frac{dE_{KS}}{dn_i^\sigma}.$$

Therefore, ϵ_a^σ is called eigenenergy. The experimentally observed energy (quasiparticle energy) corresponds to variations by 1 in n_i^σ , which doesn't strictly correspond to the differential value. However, ϵ_a^σ is a fairly good approximation of the quasiparticle energy and is widely used to evaluate the energy dispersion of a solid. Moreover, the quasiparticle energies in crystals can be obtained by the *GW* method.

The electron distribution of an atom was considered and the spin index σ was omitted in the following calculation. Assuming a spherically symmetric electron distribution, the atomic density distribution can be separated into the radial direction r

and the angular direction \hat{r} . The wave function can be written using the quantum numbers n, l, m as

$$\psi_a(\mathbf{r}) = \phi_{nl}(r)Y_{lm}(\hat{r}).$$

The radial wave function $\psi_{nl}(r)$ satisfies the following differential equation,

$$-\frac{1}{2r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left[r^2 \frac{d}{dr} \psi_{nl}(r) \right] + \left[\frac{l(l+1)}{2r^2} + V_{ext}(r) - \epsilon_{nl} \right] \phi_{nl}(r) = 0.$$

This equation has multiple solutions for the same l , meaning the number of nodes in $\psi_{nl}(r)$ (the number of nodes that cut off 0), and ϵ_{nl} becomes larger as n increases. $l=0, 1, 2, 3$ are s, p, d, f orbitals, where $n+l=l=1,2,3$ together called $(n+l)l$ orbitals (1s orbitals, 3d orbitals...).

The electron density assuming the spherically symmetric electron distribution can be obtained by allowing the partial occupancy of the orbitals and packing the electrons in the order of the orbitals with lower ϵ_{nl} ,

$$n^\sigma(r) = \sum_{nl}^{occupied} \sum_{m=-l}^l |\phi_{nl}(r)|^2 = \sum_{nl}^{occupied} (2l+1) |\phi_{nl}(r)|^2.$$

$V_{KS}(r)$ is obtained from $n(r)$ that can be calculated from $\phi_{nl}(r)$. Therefore, the electronic state can be evaluated by solving for self-consistency of $n(r)$ with the iterative method.

The localized and local atomic orbitals centred on atomic positions can be considered in solids. For instance, Gaussian [21], SIESTA [22], and OpenMX [23] are the first-principles packages that describe the wave function of molecules and solids by a linear combination of localized or local atomic orbitals.

Once the wavefunctions are obtained, the expected value of the spread of the wavefunction of each orbital of the isolated atom can be obtained from $r_{nl}^2 = \langle \psi_{nl}^\sigma | r^2 | \psi_{nl}^\sigma \rangle - \langle \psi_{nl}^\sigma | r | \psi_{nl}^\sigma \rangle^2$. The second term becomes 0 when the atomic position is placed at the origin. In addition, r_{nl} can be defined as $r_{nl} = \operatorname{argmax}_r |\psi_{nl}(r)|^2$. [24]

Furthermore, hybridization little occurs between orbitals with significantly different orbital energies, and the bonding orbital between the hybridized orbitals contribute to lowering of the total energy, i.e., stabilization. Thus, features derived from atomic orbitals (atomic quantum numbers) are useful for analyzing such cases.

1.7 Database-derived Element Features

The typical features of each element, such as the covalent bond radius and van der Waals (vdW) radius, from various crystals and molecules were evaluated. The atomic radii r_A, r_B was determined such that $R_{AB} = r_A + r_B$ for species A and B. The covalent radius evaluated the bond length from the covalent crystals [25]. On the contrary, the vdW radius was evaluated from R_{AB} between molecules forming vdW bonds in the molecular crystals. Moreover, the vdW radius evaluation is a complex case-by-case process [26], [27]. In addition, the covalent radius can be indirectly defined from the covalent bond energy rather than the atomic positions [28].

Electronegativity (χ) evaluated the features from the dissociation energies of various molecules [29]. For the variation in dissociation energy (Δ) of a molecule,

$$\Delta = E(A - B) - \frac{E(A - A) + E(B - B)}{2},$$

$$|\chi_A - \chi_B| = 0.28\sqrt{\Delta}$$

can be evaluated from $E(A - B)$, $E(A - A)$ and $E(B - B)$, which are the dissociation energy of the molecule made of element A and element B, and A-A and B-B molecules. Further normalization rendered it dimensionless and was converted from relative differences to absolute values with respect to the element H.

Moreover, χ was originally a "descriptor" that was introduced to explain the dissociation energies $E(A - B)$ from the dissociation energies $E(A - A)$ and $E(B - B)$, but [30] it is being currently used in the opposite way as a highly useful indicator of the characteristics of an element.

1.8 Atomic Positions-derived features

The descriptor features used in machine learning classical potentials are famous for their atomic position-derived features. They can reflect minor changes in atomic positions as accurately as the first-principles calculations.

1.8.1 Features in Machine Learning Classical Potential

Smooth overlap of atomic potential (SOAP) features are generated from the atomic distribution [2]. The total "density distribution" can be first defined by the atomic extended positions

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{I_p} \rho_{I_p}(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}_{I_p}),$$

where the SOAP uses

$$\rho_{I_p}(\mathbf{r}) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2}(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}_{I_p})^2\right).$$

At this moment, the dependence of the atomic index has been eliminated and is

invariant to atomic reordering. Using the expansion basis $g_n(r)$ in the radial direction, the angular basis function Y_{lm} , and orthonormalizing the basis for simplicity, $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ can be expanded by the expansion factor c_{nlm} [31].

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{nlm} c_{nlm} g_n(r) Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)$$

However, c_{nlm} has a dependence on rotation. Thus, considering $Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)$ as real spherical harmonics and converting it to variable p ,

$$p_{nn'l} = \sum_m c_{nlm} c_{n'lm},$$

where p is invariant to rotation and is called the partial power spectrum, which is regarded as the descriptor feature of the crystal. Furthermore, a different $\rho_{iI}(r)$ is defined for each element when there is more than one element.

In the original SOAP study, (r, θ, ϕ) was mapped onto a 4D hypersphere and expanded with 4D spherical harmonics. In addition, more complex bispectrum coefficients were used as p to eliminate the angular dependence [2].

Spectral nighbor analysis potential (SNAP) [11] transforms the relative atomic positions with \mathbf{R}_I as the origin and generates features of an atom I , where

$$\rho_{Ip}(\mathbf{r}) = \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{R}_{Ip}).$$

Behler's symmetry function [3] is an atomic feature around atom I and is generated from the local relative atomic positions around the site I . The two- and three-body functions utilize the relative atomic position, $\mathbf{R}_{IJq} = \mathbf{R}_{Jq} - \mathbf{R}_I$, and relative angles

$\theta_{I,Jq,Kr} = \mathbf{R}_{I,Jq} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{I,Kr} / (R_{I,Jq} R_{I,Kr})$ from the central atom of site I . In the first study, they were defined as

$$G_I^2 = \sum_{Jq} \exp(-\eta(R_{IJq} - R_c)) f_C(R_{IJq}),$$

$$G_I^4 = 2^{1-\eta} \sum_{JqKr} (1 + \lambda \cos(\theta_{I,Jq,Kr}))^\zeta \exp(-\eta(R_{IJq}^2 + R_{Jq,Kr}^2 + R_{I,Kr}^2)) f_C(R_{IJq}) f_C(R_{Jq,Kr}) f_C(R_{I,Kr}),$$

where $f_C(r)$ is a smooth cutoff function that provides a cutoff of zero over a certain distance. Moreover, the symmetry functions are generated for each atomic element combinations when there are multiple atomic elements.

Please refer [31], [32] for a recent review paper on the progress of machine learning classical potentials.

1.8.2 Features describing various elements

The material properties of various stable atomic configurations comprising various elements can be described with appropriate representation. The number of nearest-neighbor atoms (coordination number) was employed, which is a widely known concept used to describe properties in condensed matter physics and chemistry. Although the coordination number is a qualitative definition in itself, it can be quantitatively expressed by defining the contribution $\frac{\theta_{I,Jq}}{\theta_{max}}$ for each atom using the steric angle $\theta_{I,Jq}$ of the Voronoi polyhedron of atom Jq , as observed from the atom I , where θ_{max} is $\max_{Jq} \theta_{I,Jq}$.

As the feature size was extremely large, it was reduced based on the coordination number of each atomic type and using chemical knowledge such as alkali atoms being similar to each other. Let the category of atoms I, J be index a, b . The l -dependent valence electron number of the atoms of ($s^1, s^2, p^1, \dots, p^6, d^1, \dots, d^{10}, f^1, \dots, f^{14}$) were used as categories in the original orbital field matrix (OFM) [33], [34]. Furthermore, the row of the periodic table was added to the category in matminer [4].

The OFM [33] and OFM1 [34] defines the matrix elements as

$$OFM_{ab} = \delta_a(I) \left(\sum_{Jq} \zeta(R_{I,Jq}) \frac{\theta_{I,Jq}}{\theta_{max}} \delta_b(Jq) \right)$$

$$O_{ab}^c = \delta_a(I)$$

$$OFM1_{ab} = (O_{ab}^c, OFM_{ab}),$$

where $\delta_a(i)$ returns 1 if i is in category a and returns 0 otherwise. Herein, $\zeta(r)$ is a function introduced to distinguish between elements of the same category as a function of distance r . In OFM1, O_{ab}^c was introduced to identify the central atom.

OFM and OFM1 are atomic descriptor features (Atomic-OFM) if the sum of the atoms in a crystal is not considered, and they were used in the Kernel Ridge regression for the local magnetization of site I . The atomic-summed OFM is hereby denoted as Crystal-OFM, which has also been used in the Kernel Ridge regression for crystal target variables.

1.8.3 Miscellaneous Features

From the connected structure of an atom-free space, two-dimensional persistent diagram descriptor features indicating the birth radius and death radius can be generated. This descriptor is useful for distinguishing between glass and amorphous materials [35]. In addition, the space groups of crystals are features that can be constructed directly from the atomic coordinates. For instance, Spglib is a well-known package which searches for space groups from crystals [36]. The space group number can be a descriptor feature for high-pressure superconducting temperatures [37].

There are also features that are not used in the functional decomposition network of this study but are introduced below. For instance, substructures such as functional groups are commonly found in organic molecules and can be used as features (categorical quantity). Similarly, a descriptor converted to satisfy symmetry from two-dimensional images of molecules can be used [38]. Furthermore, the features can be explicitly rotated using total energy regressions with many voxel features in three dimensions [39].

1.9 Relationship between Descriptors and Crystal Target Variables

The feature generation ways were added. The features were generated from elm_i and/or \mathbf{R}_i . For instance, we generated the extended atomic position $\{\mathbf{R}_{Ip}\}$ from $\{\mathbf{S}_I\}$ in the crystal, $\{(I; \text{'extended position': } \mathbf{R}_{Ip})\}$ and generated the relative coordinates $\{\mathbf{R}_{IJq}\}$ from the extended atomic position $\{\mathbf{R}_{Ip}\}$, $\{(I; \text{'relative position': } \mathbf{R}_{IJq})\}$; further action on the Behler's two-body symmetry function produces $\{(I; \text{'Behler } G^2\text{'}: G_I^2(\{\mathbf{R}_{IJq}\})\}$.

For instance, the atomic feature $\{(I; \text{'elm': } \text{elm}_i)\}$ subjected to the electronegativity (χ) of the element-derived feature generation function obtains $\{(I; \text{'}\chi\text{'}: \chi(\text{elm}_i))\}$. If this is

converted into crystal features using the summation and maximum value methods, the crystal descriptor vector can be obtained as $(\sum_I \chi(\text{elm}_I), \max_I \chi(\text{elm}_I))$.

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